

Fig. S5. Phylogenetic sensitivity of evolutionary model fit and model parameters of mimicry accuracy evolution in Myrmarachnini and Castianeirinae. A. and B. Comparison of the corrected Akaike Information Criterion (AICc) for five alternative evolutionary models: BM, Brownian Motion; OU, Ornstein-Uhlenbeck; EB, Early Burst; FPK, Fokker-Planck-Kolmogorov; 0, white noise. C. and D. Delta AICc values. E. and F. AICc weights. G. and I. Evolutionary rate of the fitted BM, OU and FPK models. H. Phylogenetic half-life calculated from the alpha of fitted OU-models relative to the total height of the phylogenetic tree.